

CULTURAL ASPECTS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract: Advertising and the texts used in it are considered one of the features of linguistic relativity. This article discusses the definitions of advertising given by representatives of various fields, as well as the similarities and differences between advertising and advertising texts in Western and Eastern cultures, through comparing and analyzing them in two languages, especially English and Uzbek.

Keywords: Advertisements, advertising texts, culture, linguaculturology, copywriters.

Аннотация: Реклама и используемые в ней тексты считаются одним из особенностей лингвистической относительности. В данной статье обсуждаются определения рекламы, данной представителями различных областей, а также сходства и различия между рекламой и текстами рекламы в западной и восточной культурах, путем сравнения и анализа их на двух языках, в частности, на английском и узбекском.

Ключевые слова: Рекламные объявления, рекламные тексты, культура, лингвокультурология, копирайтеры.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda reklama va unda qo‘llaniladigan matnlar qiyosiy tilshunoslikning dolzarb xususiyatlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada turli soha vakillari tomonidan reklamaga berilgan ta‘riflar o‘rganilgan hamda G‘arb va Sharq madaniyatlaridagi reklama va reklama matnlari o‘rtasidagi o‘xshashlik va farqlarni ikki tilda, xususan, ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida solishtirish orqali aniqlash va ularni tahlil etishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: Reklamalar, reklama matnlari, madaniyat, lingvokulturologiya, kopirayterlar.

Nowadays, advertising is one of the most profitable business sectors, which is rapidly expanding. There are multiple vivid outdoor advertising banners and storefronts on the streets. It is rare to find a television, radio, print newspaper, or social media platform that does not contain advertisements.

Advertisements are carried out to create an image of an enterprise or person, to increase the volume of sales of products, as well as to help customers decide what to buy and why to buy it, and to encourage them to make a decision.

The master of words and pedagogue Stephan Leacock expressed a rather negative opinion about advertising: “Advertising can be called the science of stopping people's minds for a while to the extent that it is enough to extort money (Kotler, 2003)”. However, American economist Philip Kotler, who is considered the father of modern marketing, defined “Advertising as an impersonal form of communication carried out through paid media under specific sponsorship (Kotler, 2012)”, while John G. Myers, a professor of marketing in Great Britain, called advertising as follows: “Advertising is the dissemination of information about an idea, service, or product to compel the customer to act by his interests (History of advertising-An overview, n.d.)”.

Advertising can be seen as an external reflection of culture. Each country speaks to itself through hundreds of thirty-second commercials that offer a look at everyday things that surround a person through the prism of culture. Often the differences come down to simple stereotypes. There is an opinion that American advertising is unpretentious, English is distinguished by its humour, German is intrusive, and French is refined and original. Advertising text is a literary form that reflects the values of a specific target audience. Advertising text as an object of linguistic research has been studied in the last decade by domestic and foreign researchers under the principles of the linguoculturological approach. The language of advertising is considered by them as a special linguistic structure that develops according to its laws, as it pursues non-linguistic goals. This approach allows us to consider the diversity of discourses through the prism of linguistic mentality and national values and studies the national and cultural specific rules for organising speech communication (Altinay&Kuldeshov, 2023).

Nowadays, as the culture of most eastern countries is considered collectivist culture, it is common to see multiple advertisements in this spirit, that is, regarding child upbringing and education in Uzbekistan. Therefore, there are some sayings and proverbs to encourage parents to be attentive to the studies, or behaviour of children: “The best investment is an investment in education”, “Whatever you do, your child will do the same”, “Family is a part of society”. In the following advertisement text, it will be witnessed the promotion of a book that is named “Booknomy”.

Yangi yilni booknomy bilan boshlang va yil yarmiga qadar do‘stlaringiz bilan chet tilida gaplashing! Ushbu kitob orqali siz ingliz, rus, koreys, arab yoki turk tilini qisqa vaqtda samarali o‘rganib atigi 6 oyda erkin gapira olasiz. Darslarni o‘zingiz yoqtirgan joyda o‘zlashtira olasiz. Shunchaki kun davomida berilgan darsni 2 soat davomida

tinglaysiz va 6 oydan so‘ng, siz o‘rgangan tilingizda bemalol suhbatlasha olasiz. Booknomy kitoblariga 20-dekabrga qadar 50% lik chegirma e‘lon qilingan edi, ammo kompaniya kelayotgan ko‘plab murojaatlar tufayli 50%lik chegirmani 31-dekabrgacha uzaytirdi. Endi siz Yangi yil munosabati bilan booknomy kitoblarini 50%lik chegirma bilan sotib olishingiz mumkin. Shoshiling! Buyurtma bering! Kitobingizni qorbobo bepul yetkazib beradi. Hoziroq qo‘ng‘iroq qiling 1258 booknomy.uz Yaqinlaringiz uchun munosib sovg‘a!

Looking attentively at the advertising text of the “Booknomy”, it is mainly aimed at attracting consumers through discounts. It is known that discounts attract customers quickly. By providing information about the possibilities of the book at the beginning of the ad, copywriters tried to stimulate the buyers to act quickly and purchase the book.

Using the name of one of the relatives of consumers is also a new approach today. To create the necessary emotional mood and encourage the addressee to act more quickly, this method is becoming more popular in both European and Eastern cultures.

Your mom melted the caramel.

You dipped the apples.

Together, you made caramel apples.

And memories.

Make some memories for your family tonight. (Kraft Company Caramels)

Xayrli kun aziz onalar! Men hozir sizlarga haqiqiy chocotellaqilishni ko‘rsataman. Buning uchun bizlarga kerak oyim, non va chocotella. Nonni olamiz, chocotellani surtamiz. Diqqat bilan tinglang xuddi mendek qiling. Mana qarshingizda tayyor chocotella. Bu judayam oson. Men yemaganman bunaqa shirin chocotellani. Oyim nima deydilar?

Iimmm!

Bugunga yetar. Kamera stop! Olindimi? – Olindi.

Eng yaxshi kayfiyat, chocotella bilan boshlanar... (Chocotella pasta)

In the above two-language advertising texts, the process of preparing a certain product in the kitchen with the children’s mother is reflected, and by hearing and reading words such as “mom”, “together” and “child”, the listener will be familiar with the product. The use of words such as ideal mother, father, brother, and sister serves to create a perfect emotional connection between the product brand and the viewer. Mentioning the names of family members in advertisements in any way like in texts or videos is also an important phenomenon from a linguistic and cultural point of view.

In the advertising texts in the Uzbek language, the topic of the family is considered one of the important topics, because, in Uzbek society, the family is the main foundation

and link of the society. Therefore, the main part of Uzbek advertising, whether it is advertising medical devices or other types of advertising, is taken in the family circle. For example, let's pay attention to the advertising text of children's medicine:

Go'dakning isitmasi oshsa, butun oila xavotirga tushadi. Ibufen D bu tana haroratini pasaytiruvchi, og'riqlarni qoldiruvchi, yallig'lanishga qarshi vosita. Tarkibida shakar va bo'yoqlar mavjud emas. Ibufen D isitma, og'riq, yallig'lanishda yordamchi. Polshada ishlab chiqarilgan.

It can be concluded from the above text of the advertisement and that was made for it that the family plays an important role in the advertisement texts in the Uzbek language. However, it is banned to promote the medicine in Western countries.

It is interesting that in Western countries, it is normal to use advertising texts or information that shock the public to draw the attention of the population to social problems because such situations are accepted as natural in their mentality.

In the United States, which is one of the English-speaking countries, and in England, it is possible to witness advertising of energetic beverages and alcoholic drinks on television or outdoor advertising banners. However, such advertisements are restricted by law in our country. Article 37 of the Law on Advertising of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains special restrictions regulating the advertising of energy drinks, and Article 38 of the same law contains a strict restriction that advertising of alcohol products of any strength is not allowed (Law of the republic of Uzbekistan. On advertising, 1998).

Therefore, advertisements of this style are not found in any type of advertisements in Uzbekistan. In addition, advertisements encouraging people to drink alcoholic beverages are not accepted by society. Such advertisements, which do not correspond to the Uzbek mentality, are condemned by people.

In the advertising picture of Heineken alcohol products, you can witness pictures of beverages and unusual texts that effect people's attention span and it can be concluded that Western countries take this type of openness-based advertising for granted.

Social ads promoting a healthy lifestyle can also be seen in bilingual countries. Because advertising texts in this spirit affect people faster and encourage them to live properly. In my opinion, the defects explained under this topic are not very accurate in relation to our people. The text of the social ads related to the above topic is focused on AIDS, tobacco consumption, alcoholism and drug addiction, and the real picture of the problems they represent is fundamentally different from one another in Uzbekistan, Russia and Western countries.

Since the main purpose of advertisements is to attract the attention of customers, the images, text, music and animations used in it carry a certain meaning. When creating

an advertisement, focusing on the country in which it is to be displayed and using advertising texts and animations based on the culture of that country will ensure that the advertisement is effective.

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